

- 6 K. NAGANO, H. KINOSHITA and A. HIROKAWA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Tokyo)*, 1964, 12, 1198.
7. J. HVOSLEF, *Acta Chem. Scand*, 1958, 12, 1568.
8. L. H. JONES, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, 27, 665.
9. I. S. AHUJA and R. SINGH, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1974, 10, 421.
10. D. A. DOWS, A. HAIM and W. K. WILMORTH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, 21, 33.
11. A. R. DAVIS, C. J. NURPHY and R. A. PLANE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, 9, 423.
12. I. S. AHUJA and A. CARG, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, 34, 2929.
13. R. A. BAILLY, S. L. KOZAK, T. W. MICHELSEN and M. M. MILLS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, 6, 47.
14. I. S. AHUJA, R. SINGH and C. P. RAI, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1971, 8, 117.

Photochemical Reduction of Ferric Oxalate in a Solid pressed Potassium Bromide Disk

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Manuscript received 6 June 1986, revised 19 October 1987,
accepted 30 December 1987

IN continuation of our work on the photochemical reaction in solid pressed potassium bromide disk^{1,2}, we have studied the photochemical reaction of ferric oxalate.

Experimental

The transparent potassium bromide disks were prepared by mixing ferric oxalate (1 mg) with KBr (1 g) in a vibrator and the mixture was pressed under vacuum into disk (250 mg; 14.5 mm dia × 1.0 mm). The disk was irradiated with ultraviolet light from a Phillips 125 W uv lamp for 1 and 2 h and infrared spectra were recorded after each irradiation on a Perkin-Elmer 377 grating spectrophotometer, to follow the course of photochemical reactions.

Results and Discussion

The reaction products were identified by characterising the ir spectra of ferric oxalate before and after the irradiation and by chemical means. The results were also compared with the ir spectra of the disk acting as control by keeping the disk in dark and taking their spectra after 0, 1 and 2 h. No change in the position of the bands were observed, which indicates that no reaction has taken place in the dark.

The comparison of spectra before and after irradiation revealed shift of the position of several bands, and some of the bands disappeared and some new bands appeared. Gradual appearance of a

band at 2 350–2 330 cm⁻¹ was assigned to the formation of carbon dioxide³. It is observed that a broad band centered at 1 670 cm⁻¹ shifted to 1 635 cm⁻¹ (C=O)⁴. A broad band at 1 430 cm⁻¹ gradually disappeared and lost after 2 h of irradiation. The bands at 1 345 and 1 270 cm⁻¹ shifting to 1 360 and 1 315 cm⁻¹ were attributed to the $\nu_{\sigma-O} + \nu_{\sigma-\sigma}$ and $\nu_{\sigma-O} + \delta_{O-\sigma-O}$, respectively. The intensity of the band at 870 cm⁻¹ increased after irradiation which was assigned to $\nu_{\sigma-O} + \delta_{O-C-O}$ band. In the same way, the band at 805 cm⁻¹ shifting to 820 cm⁻¹ was attributed to $\delta_{O-\sigma-O} + \delta_{M-O}$. A new band appeared after irradiation at 665 cm⁻¹, and shifting of the band at 490 from 530 cm⁻¹ with the increase in band intensity was attributed to $\nu_{M-O} + \nu_{O-\sigma}$.

Thus the appearance, disappearance and shifts in the position of bands revealed the reduction of ferric oxalate into ferrous oxalate with the formation of carbon dioxide. The formation of ferrous oxalate is further confirmed by dissolving the ferric oxalate pellet before and after irradiation in the dilute solution of potassium permanganate. The permanganate solution containing irradiated pellet decolourised slowly compared to the solution containing non-irradiated pellet, inferring that ferric oxalate is reduced to ferrous oxalate according to the following stoichiometric relationship,

References

1. B. K. MEHTA, A. DUBEY, K. C. GUPTA and M. M. BOKADIA *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1983, 39, 591.
2. B. K. MEHTA, S. SINGH and A. BATRA, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, in the press.
3. J. N. PITTS, Jr., J. K. S WAN and E. A. SCHUCK, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 3606.
4. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination compounds", 2nd. ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970, pp. 244–46.

Kinetics of Oxidation of Thiocyanate Ion by Dichloramine-B in Partially Aqueous Medium

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Manuscript received 16 July 1987, revised 18 April 1988,
accepted 25 April 1988

THE chemistry of *N*-halogeno-*N*-metalloaromatic sulphonamides is of interest due to their diverse behaviour. They are sources of halonium cations and hypohalite species¹. Dichloramine-B (DCB) in an important member of the benzene analogue

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